

THE PROBLEM OF DIFFERENTIATION OF IRONY FROM OTHER TYLISTIC DEVICES (HUMOUR, SARCASM, SATIRE)

Mamadaliva Dilbar Muhammad Vali qizi

UzSWLU Student of MA department

Safarova Zarina

Supervisor : Teacher of UzSWLU

Abstract

The literary devices of irony, satire, and humor are all unique from one another. They come from several origins. They serve various objectives and are applied in various ways. Different modes are used in the literary works. Each of them produces a distinct fun and pleasure feeling. New genres have been created by each of them. They do, however, interact in various ways, and they are frequently used interchangeably. The current article investigates these variations and parallels, drawing conclusions through inference.

Key words: irony, literal text, sarcasm, satire, humour

Introduction

'The quality of being hilarious' is what **humor** is. It speaks about "the capacity to recognize and articulate a sense of the clever or humorous." **Humor** primarily consists of noticing and expressing oddities or inconsistencies in a situation or character. It is often used to highlight a fundamental absurdity in human nature or behavior and is typically regarded as a nice quality: a friendly and mellow style of humor. ¹

"The quality of being amusing or comic, especially as expressed in literature or speech," is what it is defined as. It is the capacity to convey **humor** or amuse others. ²

¹ Retrieved from <<http://www.thefreedictionary.com/humour>>

² Retrieved from <<http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/humour>>

Main part

Irony is when a word or phrase is used to convey a meaning that is contrary to its literal meaning. It is a tactic for showing, for example through character or plot development, an objective or attitude that is different from what is actually or allegedly stated. Irony is a technique used to show detachment from a subject, theme, or emotion by structuring a work in a way that fully expresses opposing or complementary emotions, attitudes, etc.³

Satire is the use of irony, sarcasm, mockery, or other similar devices to reveal, condemn, or mock wrongdoing, foolishness, etc. It is a piece of literature, either in verse or prose, in which human foolishness and immorality are exposed for mockery or ridicule. Satire is frequently compared to irony, burlesque, caricature, parody, etc. Satire describes literary genres that make fun of vices or foolishness. Satire is a generic phrase that frequently stresses a person's weakness rather than their own, and it typically connotes moral judgment and a desire to correct: Swift's critique of the petty and animalistic nature of people. Satire, irony, and sarcasm all serve to make fun of someone or something. Irony's key characteristic is the subtly conveyed contradiction between an action or expression and the situation in which it happens. The conflict between a statement's intended meaning and its literal meaning is highlighted in the figure of speech. When someone says "Beautiful weather, isn't it?" when it's pouring or unpleasant outside, the contrary is implicitly inferred. In addition to the rhetorical figure, ironic literature often emphasizes the absurdity inherent in the conflict between substance and form by using devices like character development, situation, and plot to highlight the paradoxical nature of reality or the contrast between an ideal and actual condition, set of circumstances, etc.

Satirical language lacks the complexity and wit of irony. In sarcasm, derision or mockery is used aggressively, frequently in a vulgar and disdainful manner, with harmful effects. It can be used directly or indirectly, with irony, as in "What a fine

³ Retrieved from <<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/irony>>

musician you turned out to be!" or "You couldn't play one piece correctly if you had the time in the world Satire and irony, which originated as literary and rhetorical forms, are displayed in the structure or structuring of either language or literary material, but sarcasm is unique in the spoken word and primarily manifested by voice inflection. Satire is frequently directed against prominent persons or institutions, customary behavior, political events, etc., and typically entails the use of irony or sarcasm for censorious or critical goals.

Humor is achieved through irony. The majority of contemporary fiction and literature in general use this rhetorical approach. It is frequently employed in psychologically oriented literary works, such as James Joyce's literature. As we mentioned above, Irony is a discrepancy or incongruity between what is said and what is understood, or between what is anticipated and what really happens. It might be applied purposefully or unintentionally. The audience's role is crucial. Authors can use irony to underline a key point or to make their audience pause and consider what has just been said. Irony can only be used effectively if the audience recognizes the discrepancy between what is said and what is customary or anticipated.

In its broadest sense, irony refers to a rhetorical device, literary approach, or occurrence marked by an apparent discrepancy between reality and appearance. It is common practice to emphasize a point by using verbal, dramatic, and situational irony. The sarcastic simile, which is utilized in sarcasm, and some types of litotes can be used to accentuate meaning by purposefully using language that says the opposite of the truth, rejects the contrary of the truth, or dramatically and plainly understates a factual link. Humor is the content, irony is the tool for argumentation and reasoning, and satire is the mind/wits. Satire is a literary genre, as well as occasionally graphic and performance arts, in which vices, follies, abuses, and failings are exposed for what they are, with the hope that people and society as a whole may be shamed into betterment. Although satire is typically intended to be humorous, its main objective is frequently constructive social critique. It does this by utilizing wit as a weapon and a tool to attract

attention to both specific and more general social issues. Strong irony and sarcasm are typical in satire—"in satire, irony is militant"—but other devices like parody, burlesque, exaggeration, juxtaposition, comparison, and double entendre are also commonly utilized. This "militant" irony or sarcasm frequently declares support for the very things the satirist is trying to criticize (or at least accepts as normal). Nowadays, satire may be found in a variety of artistic mediums, including lyrics, plays, commentary, television, and literature. Satire is a literary technique that uses humor, irony, exaggeration, or mockery to reveal and critique the stupidity and depravity of a person or a society. By exposing the humanity's mistakes and flaws, it seeks to make it better. In satire, a writer uses a fictional persona to represent actual people in order to expose and denounce their corruption. Satire can be directed against an individual, a nation, or even the entire planet. A satire is typically a humorous piece of writing that ridicules someone or something in order to highlight their ignorance and flaws. He also demands that those he criticizes strengthen their character by conquering their flaws.

Irony and satire go hand in hand. Irony is when what is said or done differs from what is genuinely intended. As a result, satire is commonly used by authors to bring out the dishonesty and foolishness of people and society and to condemn them by making fun of them. The majority of political cartoons that we often see in newspapers and periodicals are works of satire. These cartoons make lighthearted fun of some current political officials' behavior. Satire can be seen in some television programs, such as "The Daily Show," "The Colbert Report," and "The Larry Sanders Show." These programs allegedly try to expose what they consider to be foolish political and social perspectives. Satire is used extensively in "Huckleberry Finn" by Mark Twain. In order to express his thoughts and opinions about slavery, human nature, and several other problems plaguing American society at the time, he employs satire as a technique. Alexander Pope satirized the upper middle class of eighteenth-century England in his poem "The Rape of the Lock," which is an example of literary satire. It highlights the

conceit and frivolity of young, stylish ladies and gentlemen. Pope, for instance, writes about Belinda after she lost a lock of hair:

“Whether the nymph shall break Diana’s law,
Or some frail china jar receive a flaw,
Or stain her honor, or her new brocade”

The statement makes fun of the ideals of the affluent class of the day. The insignificant things were equated with the important things. Losing her virtue equates to a China jar breaking in Belinda's eyes. One of the best satirical novels in English literature is "Gulliver Travels" by Jonathan Swift. Swift consistently pokes fun at Western culture, religion, and politics.

Although irony and satire are frequently related, there are significant differences between the two. Satire is a style of criticism that achieves its objectives through humor. Irony is one tool used in satire. Irony focuses on the contradictions between what is stated or perceived and what is truly intended. Because satire frequently employs irony, the two rarely differ from one another.⁴

Satire and irony can both be found in works of fiction, television, film, theater, and even visual art. Irony is a tactic, whereas satire is a genre. Irony and satire are not mutually exclusive, despite the fact that they are frequently used together. Irony can be seen in dramatic and humorous art as well as satire. Similar to this, satire employs a variety of other humorous and rhetorical devices, such as ridicule, to achieve its objective. A type of humorous critique is satire. Although it occasionally employs tactics that appear harsh, its goal is not to inflict cruelty but rather to highlight flaws in the human condition, government, society, and/or individuals. Satire is an attempt to expose these flaws in order to either force change or awareness. Satire uses irony to produce a hilarious comment, much like a comedy uses jokes to make people laugh or an action movie uses explosions to thrill the audience. There are many different kinds of irony, but they all get their humor from deliberate or purposeful ignorance. Perhaps

⁴ Retrieved from <<http://www.differencebetween.net/language/difference-between-irony-and-satire/>>
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

the simplest sort of irony is when words are used in a way that is different from how they are intended.

The various kinds of figurative forms of speech that numerous literary masters use are largely responsible for the beauty of literary works. One of the frequently used metaphors in speeches is irony. This is primarily due to the fact that it is used in modern literature and even performance art. Since irony is frequently utilized in satires, many people frequently confuse the two. It's true that irony is a crucial and essential part of satires. Satire and irony are very different literary concepts. 16

How are irony and humor related? According to Dews et al., the element of surprise "yielded by the disparity between what is said and what is meant" may lead to humor. According to Colston and colleagues, contrast or incongruity lies at the heart of irony. Giora contends that irony and humor both use similar fundamental processes. In other words, they both breach the "graded informativeness requirement," but they do so in different ways: a joke changes from having an unmarked meaning to having a marked meaning, whereas irony does the opposite. Reviewing the rich literature on the function of absurdity in humor would be pointless in this situation. It will be interesting to see if irony and humor can be reduced to one another's opposites. Furthermore, it is unclear whether concepts like inappropriateness, sincerity, etc. "cleanly" reduce to contrast. 18 In addition, since humor is founded (in part) on local antonymy and irony is a sort of indirect negation, both humor and irony incorporate negation as a significant component of the phenomenon. Colston contends that "contradiction" is not always present. 22 At the perlocutionary level, the relationship between irony and humor is quite obvious and supported. Toplak and Katz agree that people find it amusing when speakers use sarcasm. 23 Irony is one of the main tools of satire; to use it effectively, one needs time and a light but accurate touch.

Some readers seem to be unaware of the distinction between humor and satire. The latter has a long and illustrious history of drawing startling comparisons to provoke

thought. Although that was the intention, there isn't really a method to gauge how effective irony is.⁵

Conclusion

Overall, both irony and satire are literary devices that are frequently employed to depict things that are false in order to bring them to the attention of the public and spur awareness and change. Irony is a figure of speech that uses careful word choice and wit to represent the opposite of the truth about something. Satire is a literary form or genre that is frequently used in the form of a performance or in the use of visual arts. Since irony is a figure of speech, it can only be used in spoken and written form. However, since satire is a literary form, it can be conveyed in a multitude of ways, such as through performances, literary works like commentary, or even the accompanying artwork to editorials. Humor, as a general phrase, refers to the audience's lighthearted, playful, whimsical response to literature that results from an unanticipated departure from reason or sense, such as a play on words, smart analogy, understatement, etc. It might contain a subtle threat or criticism, but it shouldn't be taken seriously. Irony and satire can both result in humor. However, humor's primary purpose is to briefly make the reader or audience member laugh.

REFERENCES

1. Retrieved from <<http://www.thefreedictionary.com/humour>>
2. Retrieved from <<http://oxforddictionaries.com/definition/english/humour>>
3. Retrieved from <<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/irony>>
4. Retrieved from <<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/satire>>
5. Retrieved from <<http://dictionary.reference.com/browse/irony>>
6. Retrieved from <<http://shrdocs.com/presentations/15505/index.html>>
7. Retrieved from <<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Humour>>
8. Retrieved from <<https://www.ideals.illinois.edu/handle/2142/20195>>
9. Retrieved from <<http://evankingston.com/humors-uses-in-literature/>>

⁵ Toplak, M., and A. Katz. (2000). On the uses of sarcastic irony, *Journal of Pragmatics*. v. 32 (10). pp. 1467-1488.
WWW.HUMOSCIENCE.COM

10. Retrieved from <http://udleditions.cast.org/craft_ld_irony.html>
72 Raj Kishor Singh
11. Retrieved from <<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Irony>>
12. Retrieved from <<http://voices.yahoo.com/irony-literature-it-used-6386106.html?cat=2>>
13. Retrieved from <<http://literarydevices.net/satire/>>
14. Retrieved from <<http://www.questia.com/library/literature/literary-themes-and-topics/satire-in-literature>>
15. Retrieved from <<http://www.wisegeek.com/what-is-the-difference-between-satire-and-irony.htm>>
16. Retrieved from <<http://www.differencebetween.net/language/difference-between-irony-and-satire/>>
17. Dews, S., J. Kaplan, and E. Winner. (1995). Why not say it directly? The social functions of irony, *Discourse Processes*. v. 19. p. 348.
18. Giora, R. (1995). On irony and negation, *Discourse Processes* 19. pp. 256-257.
19. Ibid.
20. Raskin, V. (1985). *Semantic Mechanisms of Humor*. Dordrecht: D. Reidel.
21. Attardo, S. (1997). The semantic foundations of cognitive theories of humor, *HUMOR: International Journal of Humor Research*. v. 10 (4). pp. 395-420.
22. Colston, H. (2000). "Dewey defeats Truman": Interpreting ironic restatement, *Journal of Language and Social Psychology*. v. 19 (1). p. 1563.